

LEADCOR

LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT FOR OCCUPATIONAL
STRESS REDUCTION IN CORRECTIONAL SETTINGS

LEADCOR User's Manual

Leadership Competencies in Correctional Settings

Module II - Leadership Conceptual Background

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LEADCOR - Leadership development for occupational stress reduction in correctional setting

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Project's website - <https://www.leadership-corrections.org/>

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Module II - Leadership Conceptual Background

Overview of the Module II

Welcome to the **Module II** about **Leadership Conceptual Background!** This Module is divided into **4 Chapters**:

- **In the Chapter “Understanding Leadership Styles”,** we will focus on the **subchapters**:
 - What is Leadership?;
 - Leadership: Contemporary Theories;
 - Leadership Styles.

- **In the Chapter “The Situational Leadership Model”, we will focus on the subchapter:**
 - The Situational Leadership Model Applied to the Correctional System.

- **In the Chapter “Understanding Leadership Roles”, we will focus on the subchapters:**
 - Leadership Roles;
 - Leadership competencies.

- **In the Chapter “Essential Leadership Competencies”, we will focus on the subchapters:**
 - Emotional Intelligence;
 - Communication;
 - Goal Setting;
 - Motivating People;
 - Building Teams;
 - Conflict Management;
 - Coaching.

By the end of this module, you will be able to:

- ◆ Understand what Leadership is
- ◆ Learn the importance of Leadership
- ◆ Identify the seven Leadership styles and their differences
- ◆ Comprehend the relation between trust and Leadership
- ◆ Learn the Situational Leadership Model
- ◆ Learn the Leadership roles
- ◆ Identify the Leadership competencies
- ◆ Recognise the importance of Leadership assessment
- ◆ Learn the essential Leadership competencies

Chapter 1 - Understanding Leadership Styles

Sub-chapter 1.1 - What is Leadership?

Leadership is a process by which a person can **direct, guide and influence the behaviour and work of other people towards the achievement of specific goals** in a given situation. Leadership is the capacity of a person to induce employees to work with confidence and enthusiasm. Leadership is the potential to influence the behaviour of other people. It is also defined as the ability to influence a group towards realising a goal. Leaders are expected to create future visions and motivate the organisational members to achieve the visions. As such, Leadership is the human factor that binds a group together and motivates them towards common goals.¹

There are important characteristics of Leadership ought to be aware of:¹

01

It is an **interpersonal** process where a person influences and guides employees towards the achievement of objectives;

02

It represents a few **qualities** to be present in a person, including intelligence, maturity, and personality;

03

It is a **group process** - it includes two or more people interacting with each other;

04

A leader **shapes and moulds the behaviour of the group** towards the accomplishment of organisational goals;

05

Leadership is **situation bound** - there is no best style of Leadership. It all depends upon facing the circumstance.

Leadership is an important function of management that helps to **maximise efficiency and to achieve organisational goals**. The following aspects explain the importance of Leadership:¹

1. **Initiates action** - a leader starts the work by communicating the policies and plans to the employees from where the work begins;
2. **Motivation** - a leader proves to be playing an incentive role that concerns working. A leader motivates the employees with economic and non-economic rewards and thereby gets the work from the employees;
3. **Providing guidance** - a leader must not only supervise but also play a guiding role for the employees. Guidance here means instructing the employees on the way they must perform their work effectively and efficiently;
4. **Creating confidence** - confidence is an important factor that can be achieved by expressing the work efforts to the employees, explaining their role clearly and giving them guidelines to accomplish the objectives efficiently. It is also crucial to hear the employees concerning their complaints and problems;
5. **Building morale** - morale denotes the willing cooperation of the employees towards their work, giving them confidence and gaining their trust. A leader can be a morale promoter by reaching full cooperation to perform to the best of their skills as they work to accomplish goals;
6. **Builds work environment** - an effective work environment helps in sound and stable progress. Therefore, human relations should be kept in mind by a leader. He/she should treat employees on humanitarian terms;
7. **Coordination** - coordination is the result of reconciling personal interests with organisational goals. This synchronisation can be achieved through proper and effective coordination, which should be the primary motive of a leader.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 1.2 - Leadership: Contemporary Theories

The **Tannenbaum-Schmidt Leadership Continuum** (the name comes after the Contingency theorists Robert Tannenbaum and Warren Schmidt) identified **seven Leadership styles**. They run in a continuum, from a rigid authority, at one end, through to complete freedom for a team, at the other. Let us look at each style in turn: ¹

- **The leader that Tells** - makes the decision and expects the team to follow. This style can be valuable if you have plenty of new starters to manage. But the continued application of this style can quickly become frustrating, especially to team members that are highly qualified and experienced. So, we suggest using it only when needed.
- **The leader that Sells** - makes the decision but provides a rationale for it. The decision will not change, but the team feels that its needs are being considered.
- **The leader that Suggests** - outlines the decision, includes a rationale and asks if team members have any questions. They know that they have participated in the decision, which helps build trust.
- **The leader that Consults** - proposes a decision and then invites input and discussion, which allows the team to influence the result. This style recognises that the team has valued insight to offer, however in a setting like a prison context, this style can be difficult to implement, and the opportunities to do so can be scarce.
- **The leader that Joins** - describes the problem and asks the team for proposals about solving it. Decision-making is a cooperative process, and the team feels appreciated and trusted.
- **The leader that Delegates** - outlines the problem and permits the team to discover solutions. The team contributes to the final decision, but the leader continues to be responsible for the outcome. This style can be challenging to implement, considering the dynamics of the prison settings.

- Finally, the **leader that Abdicates** - asks the team to define the problem and determine how to solve it. The team contributes to the final decision, but the leader is still responsible for its outcomes, should it be a success or a failure.

Figure 1. Tannenbaum-Schmidt Leadership Continuum
Source: Expert Program Management

These **Leadership styles** largely relate to a team’s level of development and growth. As trust and competency increase, so does the freedom that the team members want and those leaders feel comfortable providing.

According to **Hersey and Blanchard’s Situational Theory** (the name comes after Paul Hersey and Kenneth Blanchard), the **leader must match the Leadership style according to the readiness of employees**, which has stages and a cycle. Hence, this theory is also famous as the **Life-Cycle Theory of Leadership**.^{2, 14}

Readiness is the extent to which followers are able and willing to accomplish a specific task. **Ability** is an individual's knowledge, experience, and skill to do the job (job readiness). **Willingness** is the motivation and dedication needed to achieve a certain task. The style of Leadership differs on the level of followers' readiness.

The **Readiness (R)** is divided into a continuum of **four levels**:

R1 - Low follower readiness - refers to the low ability and low willingness of followers (those who are incapable and insecure);

R2 - Low to moderate follower readiness - describes the low ability and high willingness of followers (those who are incapable but confident);

R3 - Moderate to high follower readiness - represents the high ability and low willingness of followers (those who are capable but insecure);

R4 - High follower readiness - describes followers' high ability and high willingness (those who are both able and confident).

Figure 2. Readiness (R) four levels

The leader provides the direction at the lower levels of readiness. Hence, the decisions are leader directed. On the other hand, the followers give direction at higher readiness levels. Consequently, in this case, the decisions are follower directed. When the

followers change from low levels to high levels of readiness, it begins to change the combinations of task and relationship behaviours appropriate to the situation.

For each of the four readiness levels, the used leadership style may be a combination of **task** and **relationship behaviour**.

Task behaviour - the extent to which the leader explains the responsibilities of a follower, which involves giving them direction, establishing objectives, and identifying roles for them. Normally, a one-way communication happens, which is meant to give followers direction.

Figure 3. Task and Relationship Behaviour

Relationship behaviour - the extent to which the leader listens to the followers and encourages them. Here, two-way communication exists between the leader and the follower.

By combining the task and the relationship behaviour, we reach the next four different **styles of Leadership**, which relate to the different levels of readiness:

S1 - Telling: This style is most suitable for low follower readiness (R1). It emphasises high task behaviour and limited relationship behaviour;

S2 - Selling: This style is most suitable for low to moderate follower readiness (R2). It emphasises high amounts of both task and relationship behaviour;

S3 - Participating: This style is most suitable for moderate to high follower readiness (R3). It emphasises a high amount of relationship behaviour but a low amount of task behaviour;

S4 - Delegating: This style is most suitable for high follower readiness (R4). It emphasises low levels of both task and relationship behaviour.

Figure 4. Four Different Styles of Leadership

Transformational Leadership introduces **four elements** to be considered:³

Figure 5. Transformational Leadership Four Elements

1. Individualised Consideration – the degree to which the leader attends to each follower's needs, acts as a mentor or coach the follower and listens to the follower's worries and needs. The leader shows empathy and assistance, keeps communication open and places challenges before the followers. This element also involves the need for respect and celebrates the individual contribution that each follower can make to the team. The followers have a will and ambitions for self-development and have the motivation to perform their tasks.

2. Intellectual Stimulation – the extent to which the leader confronts assumptions, takes risks and solicits followers' opinions. Leaders with this style encourage creativity in their followers. They nurture and improve people who think independently. For such a leader, learning is a benefit, and unexpected situations are seen as learning opportunities. The followers ask questions, think about things, and find better ways to implement their tasks.

3. Inspirational Motivation – the degree to which the leader expresses an appealing and inspiring vision to followers. Leaders with inspiring motivation challenge followers with increased standards, transmit optimism around future ambitions and offer to mean for the task. Followers ought to have a strong feeling of purpose if they are to be encouraged to act. Purpose and meaning offer the strength that pushes a group forward. The visionary qualities of Leadership are supported by communication abilities that make the vision understandable, precise, powerful, and appealing. The followers are happy to invest more effort in their tasks, as they are encouraged and optimistic about the future, believing in their abilities.

4. Idealised Influence – the degree to which a leader provides high ethical behaviour, inspires pride, earns respect and trust. As a development instrument, transformational Leadership has spread in all sectors of western societies, including governmental organisations.

Transactional Leadership is most often used by leaders. It centres on the basic management process of controlling, organising, and short-term planning. It involves motivating and directing followers mainly through appealing to their self-interest. The power of transactional leaders falls in their formal authority and responsibility in the

organisation. The main objective of the follower is to follow the directions of the leader. The style can also be mentioned as a “telling style”.^{4,5}

The leader considers motivation through a system of rewards and punishment. If an employee does what is required, a reward will follow, and if he/she does not go as the leader wishes, a punishment will follow. Here, the leader and the follower exchange take place to accomplish routine performance objectives.

These exchanges include four components:^{4,5}

Figure 6. Leader and Follower Four Components Exchanges

- **Contingent Rewards:** Transactional leaders connect the goal to rewards, make clear expectations, provide necessary resources, set mutually agreed-upon goals, and offer various bonuses for effective performance. They set **SMART** (**S**pecific, **M**easurable, **A**ttainable, **R**ealistic, and **T**imely) objectives for their employees.
- **Active Management by Exception:** Transactional leaders actively manage and monitor their employees' work, watch over for any deviations from rules and requirements, and take corrective action to prevent mistakes.

- **Passive Management by Exception:** Transactional leaders intervene merely when standards are not met or when the performance is not expected. They may even use punishment as a reaction to the undesirable performance.
- **Laissez-faire:** The leader offers an environment where the employees have several opportunities to make decisions. The leader abdicates obligations and avoids making decisions, and thus the group frequently lacks direction.

The **Transactional Theory** is based on three assumptions, namely:^{4, 5}

- Employees are motivated by reward and punishment;
- The employees must obey the orders of the superior;
- The employees are not self-motivated. They must be closely monitored and controlled to get the work done.

The **Transactional Leaders** overemphasise detailed and short-term objectives and standard rules and processes. They do not make an effort to improve followers' creativity and production of new ideas. This kind of Leadership style may work well where the organisational problems are simple and clearly defined. Such leaders tend not to reward or ignore ideas that do not fit existing plans and goals.^{12, 13}

Figure 7. Transactional Leadership - Contingent Rewards

Transactional Leaders are observed to be quite effective in guiding efficient decisions to cut costs and improve productivity. Transactional leaders have a tendency to be highly directive and action-oriented, and their relationship with their followers tends to be transitory and not centred on emotional bonds.^{12, 13}

The theory assumes that simple incentives can drive employees. The only “transaction” between the leader and the followers is their income for their compliance and effort.

Differences between Transactional and Transformational Leaders:^{12, 13}

The **Transactional Leadership** style is perceived as insufficient, but not bad, in creating the highest leadership potential. It creates more mature interactions, but leaders should take care not to perform it exclusively; otherwise, it will produce an environment permeated by position, power, perks, and politics.

Figure 8. Differences between Transactional and Transformational Leaders

The concept of **Abusive Supervision** is defined as “subordinates perceptions of the extent to which supervisors engage in the sustained display of hostile verbal and nonverbal behaviours, excluding physical contact”.^{6 (p.178)} Findings suggest that **higher levels of abusive supervision were related to more significant psychological distress**. Other consequences of abusive supervision include greater Work-Family Conflict (WFC), withdrawal from the organisation and compromised well-being.⁷

Abusive supervision is firmly **positively associated with authoritarian Leadership** and **negatively related to ethical Leadership** and leader-member exchange. Moreover, a moderate to strong (negative) association was found between abusive supervision and the dimension of organisational justice, meaning that abusive supervision may be related to perceptions of unfair treatment.

Figure 9. Abuse Supervision Characteristics
Source: Shahid Khan, Central Queensland University

There are **three mechanisms to explain abusive supervision**:^{7, 15}

1. **Social learning**: according to a social learning view of abusive supervision, leaders will engage in abusive supervision because they learned to do so with role models they identify with, such as family members, upper management in the organisation they work or even through organisational norms and country culture;
2. **Identity threat**: leaders appear to be more likely to engage in abusive supervision when they feel threatened by their employees' (provocative) behaviour, when they are threatened by hierarchical superiors (and therefore use employees as safe targets to express their frustration), and when they display some characteristics such

as psychological entitlement and Machiavellianism; and Self-regulation impairment: supervisors are more abusive when they face time-based work stress, exceedingly difficult goals, need to display emotions that are inconsistent with the ones they felt and behave ethically (both acts that drain self-resources), have poor sleep quality, and conflict between work and family.

3. **Self-regulation impairment:** supervisors are more abusive when they face time-based work stress, exceedingly difficult goals, need to display emotions that are inconsistent with the ones they felt and behave ethically (both acts that drain self-resources), have poor sleep quality, and conflict between work and family.

Representative behaviours include **sabotaging, yelling, ignoring employees, publicly insulting them and hurting their feelings**. Abusive supervision has detrimental effects on employees' personal and professional life. Victims of supervisory abuse are likely to experience diminished psychological and physical well-being, such as emotional exhaustion, job tension, detachment, depression, anxiety, psychological ill health and reduced life satisfaction. These negative psychological and physical outcomes have detrimental effects on employees' attitudes and behaviours.⁸

Figure 10. Abuse Supervision Detrimental Effects

A large number of studies have reported **negative effects of abusive supervision on employees' job satisfaction**. It has also been reported to affect the employees' family satisfaction negatively. Abusive supervision also has a direct and indirect negative relationship with **employee performance** — the negative effects of abusive supervision on employee task performance via emotional exhaustion. Past research has also identified other performance-related outcomes, such as work effort, citizenship

behaviour, and resistance behaviours.⁷ As a result, these negative outcomes cost the organisation in terms of lost productivity, absenteeism, turnover and health care expenditure.

Employee performance

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 1.3 - Leadership Styles

Across the literature, there are many classifications of Leadership styles. It is possible to find different classifications during 80 years of research on this topic, each indicating a different set of traits and skills. It shows that leading can be done in many ways. **Every leader has his/her own style.** Equally, as we are not all the same people, we are naturally also not all the same leaders.¹

Leadership style is a leader's approach to offering direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. There are three basic leadership styles: Authoritarian (**Autocratic**), Participative (**Democratic**) and Delegative (**Laissez-Faire**).

Figure 11. Leadership Styles

- **Authoritarian (Autocratic) Leadership:**^{2, 3}

A leader who dictates policy and directs the work done by the group without looking for any significant feedback from them. The group led by an authoritarian would be anticipated to carry out their tasks under close supervision. Researchers discovered less creativity under an authoritarian leadership style but still maintaining productivity.

While authoritarian Leadership seems stifling, it has its place: it is best used in circumstances where there is not enough time for group decision-making or when the leader has the expertise that the rest of the group does not. When authoritarian Leadership drifts into areas that are not required, it can generate dysfunctional environments where followers are the “good guys”, and domineering leaders are the “bad guys”.

- **Participative (Democratic) Leadership:**^{4, 5, 6}

Group members feel involved in the decision-making process when they have a participative leader. Those leaders practising the participative Leadership style offer guidance to the group for their input in decision making but retain the final say. **Participative leaders make their group feel like they are part of a team, creating commitment within the group.**

Findings suggest that the participative style of Leadership yielded the most desirable results. They were not quite as productive as the children in the authoritarian group, but their work was of higher quality.

There are downsides to the participative style: **if roles within the group are unclear, participative Leadership can lead to communication failures.** If the group is not qualified in the area in which they are making decisions, inadequate decisions could result.

- **Delegative (Laissez-Faire) Leadership:**^{7, 8}

Leaders practicing the delegative leadership style are very hands-off. **They offer little or no supervision to their group and leave the decision-making up to them.** A delegative leader will offer the required tools and resources to complete a project and take responsibility for the group’s decisions and activities, but power is delivered to the group.

It was found that a group of children attempting to achieve the craft project under the delegative leader were, compared to others, the least productive. This group also made more demands of their leader, they were not able to work independently and showed little cooperation.

The delegative style is especially suitable for a group of highly skilled employees, and creative teams frequently value this type of freedom. Alternatively, this style does not work well for a group that requires the needed motivation, skills, or adherence to deadlines, leading to inadequate performance.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

What did I learn?

- ◆ The definition and characteristics of Leadership
- ◆ The importance of Leadership
- ◆ The seven Leadership styles identified by the Tannenbaum-Schmidt Leadership Continuum
- ◆ Hersey and Blanchard's Situational Theory
- ◆ The definition and characteristics of Transformational Leadership
- ◆ The definition and characteristics of Transactional Leadership
- ◆ The definition and characteristics of Abusive Supervision
- ◆ The definition and characteristics of Authoritarian (Autocratic) Leadership
- ◆ The definition and characteristics of Participative (Democratic) Leadership
- ◆ The definition and characteristics of Delegative (Laissez-Faire) Leadership

Chapter 2 - The Situational Leadership Model

Sub-chapter 2.1 - The Situational Leadership Model applied to the correctional system

Situational leadership is a way of adjusting one's management style to adapt to each situation or task and the needs of the team or team member. In this model, the leader is flexible in their approach and uses different leadership strategies depending on the situation. This approach to leadership indicates the necessity to match two key aspects properly: **the leader's leadership style and the followers' maturity or preparedness levels.**¹

The key to successful leadership is to combine the proper leadership style with the corresponding maturity level of the employees. Each of the **four leadership styles** is suitable for the corresponding employee maturity level:^{1,2}

- **The Telling style** works best for leading employees at the M1 level (low competence, low commitment);
- **The Selling style** works best for leading employees at the M2 level (low competence, high commitment);
- **The Participating style** works best for leading employees at the M3 level (high competence, low commitment/confidence);
- **The Delegating style** works best for leading employees at the M4 level (high competence, high commitment/confidence).

Figure 12. Four Leadership Styles and Corresponding Employee Maturity Level

Recognising the **employee maturity level** is a significant part of the process. The leader must have the commitment and ability to use any four leadership styles as needed.¹

Figure 13. Maturity Levels

The **Situational Leadership Theory** implies that the most effective leadership style is impacted by situations where leaders find themselves. They argue that **a leader's capability to lead depends upon specific situational factors**. By understanding, realising, and adjusting to these factors, leaders will be able to influence their environments and followers more successfully than if these aspects are ignored. More specifically, **the followers' characteristics greatly focus on establishing appropriate Leadership behaviours**. They discovered that leaders would have to change their leadership style as their followers altered in terms of their ability (**Task Readiness**) and willingness (**Psychological Readiness**) to execute the required task.¹ Therefore, a leader's relationship with followers is likely to go through different stages as these abilities and willingness can change over time.

An Important Note About Hersey and Blanchard:¹

Although Hersey and Blanchard worked together for years to maintain the idea that leadership styles should be situational, **they decided to go individual ways to concentrate on their agendas**. Thus, the **Hersey and Blanchard Situational Leadership Model** was developed into **two slightly divergent models**.

Figure 14. Hersey and Blanchard Situational Leadership Divergent Models
Source: Business-to-you

Blanchard chose to call his version “The Situational Leadership II Model” (or SLII Model). The major differences are associated with semantics: where Hersey used the word ‘**Readiness (R)**’, Blanchard chose to use ‘**Development (D)**’. And Hersey used ‘**Telling**’, ‘**Selling**’ and ‘**Participating**’, Blanchard used ‘**Directing**’, ‘**Coaching**’ and ‘**Supporting**’, respectively.

- **Follower’s Task Readiness (Task Development):**

A follower’s Task Readiness includes their capability to provide what has been asked of them. Their abilities, knowledge, and competencies will affect their delivery of a task independently of a leader’s management. Blanchard chose to use the term development instead of readiness as followers are prone to ‘grow’ in their abilities through time. Furthermore, Blanchard utilised the word **competence** (meaning skills, knowledge and abilities) instead of Hersey’s term **Ability**.

- **Follower's Psychological Readiness (Psychological Development):**

A follower's or employee's Psychological Readiness is the extent to which they are willing to take on responsibility for their acts. This may include factors such as motivation, drive, energy, and confidence in their own skill. For this, Blanchard used the word **Commitment** (meaning confidence and motivation) as an alternative to Hersey's term **Willingness**.

Figure 15. Follower's Psychological Readiness

- **R1 (D2): Unable and Unwilling (Low Competence and Low Commitment):** A follower with a **R1**-status is unable to complete the required task, because they do not possess the necessary set of skills to perform well. Moreover, they are either unwilling to deliver the required task or lack self-confidence. Note that Blanchard labelled this follower style with D2 instead of D1. The reason behind this choice is that Blanchard views this follower style as the second stage in a follower's evolutionary development.
- **R2 (D1): Unable and Willing (Low Competence and High Commitment):** A **R2** follower is just like a **R1** follower unable to perform a certain task, but in contrast to a **R1** follower, willing to try anyway. In other words: they are motivated to attempt the task even though they lack the skills, knowledge and/or ability to do so. This follower style is often seen with new employees who are keen to

impress their supervisor, but still lack the work experience to be productive right from the start. Because of this, Blanchard decided to label this follower style with D1, as it is likely to be the first stage of a follower's development. As followers gain experience, they reach development level 2 (D2) and gain some competence, but their commitment drops because the task may be more complex than the follower had originally perceived at the start of the task.

- **R3 (D3): Able and Unwilling (High Competence and Low Commitment):** R3 followers are likely to be able to perform well on their task, since they have developed the necessary skill set. The problem, however, is that they are unwilling to do so. The reason for this behaviour are twofold: followers could be unmotivated to comply with the leader's request or could (still) be nervous about performing the task without enough support and encouragement from the leader. In Blanchard's vocabulary of the D3 follower style, commitment is variable as it starts off as low, but gradually grows bigger due to more self-esteem and confidence until a follower reaches D4.
- **R4 (D4): Able and Willing (High Competence and High Commitment):** Lastly, we have the R4 followers: they are ready, able, and willing to perform. This means that followers are experienced at the required task and comfortable with their own ability to do it well and independently. They are able and willing to not only do the task, but to take responsibility for it. In this stage, both competence and commitment are considered, to be high in terms of Blanchard's version of the Situational Leadership Model.

Based on these distinct follower styles, leaders should adjust their leadership style to meet the necessities of their employees. Leaders can do it by discovering the adequate balance between **Directive and Supportive behaviour**. A leader's directive behaviour will be somewhere on a high to low spectrum and reflect the "**concern for production**" dimension. This implies to what extent a leader emphasises the concern to get the job completed by being task-focused. The proper level of directive behaviour that leaders will have to decide depends on followers' readiness or development level.

- **Leader’s Supportive Behaviour:**

A leader’s supportive behaviour reflects the “**concern for people**” dimension. This means to what extent a leader emphasises building and maintaining a good relationship with employees by paying attention to the employees’ security, well-being, and personal needs. The proper level of this relationship-focused approach is like the directive behaviour determined by followers’ readiness or development level.

- **S1: Telling (Directing):**^{3, 4}

The S1 leadership style puts a high emphasis on directive behaviour and a low emphasis on supportive behaviour. A leader’s primary concern lies with the task delivery and less with the employees’ personal needs. Typical behaviour for an S1 leadership style is offering step-by-step instructions, a clear description of the effects of non-performance and close supervision. In such a condition, it is essential that the task is clearly described, and the phases of the process are easy to follow. This is significant because the leader considers the follower (R1) either does not understand what to do or is unwilling and needs, thus, a certain level of coercive power.

On the other hand, this style should be used for D1 followers who are highly “**Enthusiastic Beginners**”. They already have the motivation to perform the tasks needed, which lowers the necessity for supportive behaviour. But they still do not have the competence, which increases their need for directive behaviour.

- **S2: Selling (Coaching):**^{3, 4}

This high directive and high supportive S2 Leadership style is required for R2 followers who are willing but unable to perform a task. The leader’s style ought to be concerned with improving the confidence and skills of followers so they can eventually develop more responsibility for their actions. However, it is also believed that this style is necessary for D2 followers, who initially were highly enthusiastic but lost

confidence because their competencies were failing them. Therefore, these “Disillusioned Learners” need a leader with a greater concern for supportive behaviour that helps them gain confidence and become motivated again.

- **S3: Participating (Supporting):**^{3, 4}

The S3 leadership style relates to both R3 and D3 followers. This style reveals high supportive behaviours however low directive behaviours. This may include listening, praise and a high level of contact between leader and follower. Also, the leader sets a high level of trust in the follower to accomplish the daily tasks as the follower’s competence has also increased throughout time. Therefore, the leader will only encourage and offer feedback when needed to motivate and develop the employee, but not comment on the task performance. This is because the leader considers that the follower can achieve the required tasks largely independently.

- **S4: Delegating:**^{3, 4}

The final leadership style assumes low supportive and low directive behaviour and applies to R4 and D4 followers. This is a “hands-off approach” as the employee is able and willing to execute the tasks independently and with high responsibility. The leader can encourage autonomy while monitoring, not overloading the follower with responsibility and not withdrawing entirely from the follower’s closeness. It is essential for this type of follower to keep observing and monitoring them (although to a far lesser extent).

Figure 16. Leaders’ Directive Behaviour
Source: Albright Global

Figure 17. Leaders' Directive Behaviour Development Levels
Source: Business-to-you

Here are some of the **characteristics of the Situational Leadership style:**¹

- **Insight** - the situational leader must be able to understand the needs of the followers, then adjust his/her management style to meet those needs;
- **Flexibility** - situational leaders must be able to move seamlessly from one type of leadership style to another;
- **Trust** - the leader must be able to gain his/her followers' trust and confidence;
- **Problem-solving** - this leader must be able to resolve problems, for example, how to get a job done utilising the best leadership style available;
- **Coach** - this leader must evaluate the followers' maturity and competence and use the proper strategy to develop the followers and their personal character.

Four Contextual Key Factors:

Experts suggest four key contextual factors that leaders must be aware of when assessing the situation.

Figure 18. Key Contextual Factors - Assessing the Situation

- **Consider the Relationship:²**

Leaders should consider the relationship between them and the group members. Social and interpersonal aspects can play a role in establishing which approach is best.

For example, a group lacking efficiency and standard procedures might benefit from a style that emphasises order, rules and clearly specify roles. A group of highly competent employees, on the other hand, might gain from a more democratic style that permits group members to work independently.

- **Consider the Task:²**

The leader needs to think about the task. Tasks can vary from simple to complex, but the leader must have a clear idea of what the task entails to establish if it has been successfully and competently completed.

- **Consider the Level of Authority:²**

The leader's level of authority over the group members should also be taken into consideration. Some leaders have power given by the position itself, such as the capacity to fire, hire, reward, or reprimand employees. Other leaders achieve power through relationships with employees, frequently by acquiring their respect, offering support, and being included in the decision-making process.

- **Consider the Level of Maturity:²**

Leaders need to think about the level of maturity of each group member. The maturity level measures an individual's ability to complete a task and his/her willingness to achieve it. Designating a job to a willing member who lacks the capability is a formula for failure.

Determining each employee's maturity level allows the leader to decide the best leadership style to assist employees in accomplishing their goals.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

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What did I learn?

- ◆ Definition and characteristics of the Situational Leadership
- ◆ The four leadership styles for the corresponding employee maturity level
- ◆ The Follower's Task Readiness
- ◆ The Follower's Psychological Readiness
- ◆ A Leader's Supportive Behaviour

Chapter 3 - Understanding Leadership

Roles

Sub-chapter 3.1 - Leadership Roles

Leading can be done in many ways; there is not only one way to do it, nor is it better or “the right” one. **There are many roles a person can undertake, cumulatively or individually, to help foster the development towards a common goal.** In everyday work in the organisation and on projects, there are multiple roles a leader can find himself/herself in.¹

The first thing that is always discussed when leaders are mentioned is **creating a vision**. Leaders often take the role of creating an inspiring vision that others would follow. A vision establishes shared values and should give direction and set goals for others to understand, should they wish to follow. Whenever there is a common project in progress or a goal to reach, your task as a leader is to be prepared and to lead through the changes. Good leaders manage change strategically, take risks, and even create change themselves.¹

When the group is resistant, the leader’s role is to manage the resistance and lead by example. **The leader's number one advice we can give to you** is to “practice what you preach” to set an example for people looking up to you. Leaders earn the trust of their group by demonstrating confidence and sharing hardships and risks. Good leaders win respect and trust without courting popularity.¹

The second important category of leadership roles focuses on **motivating the team**, the people around you. Be enthusiastic. Let your energy be the first thing you will bring to the table. People are inspired by motivating examples and are more ready to follow such a lead. By way of example, let your people be inspired and energised, assuring you create a positive work environment. By being open-minded, open to the ideas of others, you will manage to empower people. By empowering, we also understand delegating authority. **Communicate openly and honestly**, give clear guidelines, and set clear

expectations. Do not lead by an iron fist – a leader’s role is to empathise, be willing to discuss and solve problems, listen with understanding, support, and help.¹

Being a leader is not about you, you, you. A good leader understands it is about others. Make sure to use a team approach and **involve everyone**. The leader’s role is to facilitate cooperation between all the members and let go of control and trust the group, let yourself rely on their judgment. It is important to permit a group to decide, and in case it does not go perfectly well, it should be brought up as a good learning experience. The leader’s role is to facilitate and help the group make better decisions in the future and grow. A good leader will strive to bring out the best in people and have a common touch with them. A leader’s role is frequently to act as a coach and provide effective feedback. Leaders monitor progress but do not micromanage and dictate.¹

Figure 19. Adequate Leaders' Characteristics

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 3.2 - Leadership Competencies

Every competence starts with knowledge. To be competent at anything, it is important to have a basis in knowledge. The role of knowledge is to grasp the meaning of a thing, an event or a situation, see it in its relations to other things, note how it operates or functions, what consequences follow from it, what causes it, and what uses it can be put to.³

Leaders with information on the task at hand will make more attempts at leading than those without the proper knowledge. At the same time, as it provides valuable information, knowledge might be a strong motivator for first-time leaders to undertake an activity.

Essential knowledge: interests, concerns and needs of new staff/your team, leadership skills and styles, group dynamics, delegation, basics of management and planning, understanding of diversity and culture.³

cAttitude is a mental set that causes a person to respond characteristically to a given stimulus. Attitude is the way people view and interpret their environment. In fulfilling one's leadership capacity, optimum development occurs when one is a healthy person, showing physical and mental fitness, having a positive self-image, maintaining self-understanding, and possessing appropriate coping skills. The need for achievement, affiliation, and power are the most important needs that motivate people.

Motivation is the key to success in any field, especially true for leadership.² Essential attitudes and values are, for example, curiosity, self-awareness, confidentiality, interest in views of others, open-mindedness, trustworthiness, integrity, sensitivity to diversity.

Skill is defined as an ability and capacity acquired through deliberate, systematic, and sustained effort to carry out complex activities smoothly and adaptively involving ideas (cognitive skills), things (technical skills), and/or people (interpersonal skills).¹ In leadership, many skills make an essential part of a leader's skill portfolio. After attaining

knowledge and having the right attitude, **skills close the circle in becoming a competent leader**. Skills require time and cannot be perfected overnight. By trying, and reflecting, then trying some more, anyone can develop a satisfactory level of any skill. The great thing about skills is that we can have as much or as little as we are willing to invest in building them, but we can never have zero. The ability to lead effectively is based on several key skills, closely related to and often overlapping one with another. People have many skills they might not even be aware of, and even insignificant small ones can spike the learning of new ones.¹

Essential leadership skills:³

Pivotal skill: talking about the relation between emotional intelligence and leadership, we often notice how a good leader needs to influence others or get others to work together towards a common goal. While influencing others is a very important dimension of a leader, the internal dimension might at times be even more crucial. Leadership, however, is much of an internal as an external capacity. Internal capacity represents the ability to analyse one's own strengths and weaknesses, set personal and vocational goals, and have the self-esteem to carry them out. It includes identifying community resources and using them to live independently and establish support networks to participate in community life and to effect positive social change.³

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

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What did I learn?

- ◆ Different Leadership Roles and characteristics
- ◆ What are Skills
- ◆ Essential Leadership Skills

Chapter 4 - Essential Leadership Competencies

Sub-chapter 4.1 - Emotional Intelligence

An **organisation** consists of a group of people, and when people are involved, emotions inevitably occur - and the workplace is no different. It would be risky to believe that a workplace is logical and non-emotional. **However, emotions can be the biggest motivator or de-motivator of an employee. Emotions influence the performance and efficiency of an employee.** If not be the case, we would never talk about the importance of work-life balance and, in the present context, the need for emotionally intelligent leaders.^{1, 2}

The current times are very dynamic, both economically and socially, where the social fabric is rapidly evolving due to globalisation and other influences. The workforce's average age is reducing, and the leaders now look forward to managing people from different cultures and backgrounds. In such a situation, a leader needs to be highly sensitised to the emotional aspects of his/her transactions with people.

Emotional Intelligence is *“the ‘ability to execute precise reasoning about emotions and the ability to use emotions and emotional knowledge to improve the thought’”*.³ Basically, it is the ability to recognise and understand one’s feelings and emotions and those of others, using that information to manage emotions and relationships.

The **four important aspects of Emotional Intelligence** are:³

Self-awareness

- Emotional Self-Awareness
- Accurate Self-Assessment
- Self-Confidence

- **Emotional Self-Awareness** - the ability to know yourself and understand your feelings;
- **Accurate Self-Assessment** - understanding your strengths and weaknesses and their effects;
- **Self-Confidence** - having faith in yourself and being willing to put yourself forward.

Self-management

- Emotional Self-Control
- Initiative
- Transparency
- Adaptability
- Optimism

- **Emotional Self-Control** - an essential part of emotional maturity, controlling feelings and/or expressing them in an adequate setting is a key ability;
- **Initiative** - being self-motivated and having the ability to keep working despite setbacks;
- **Transparency** - being honest and open, interacting with integrity and being trustworthy;
- **Adaptability** - showing resilience and the ability to change course when necessary;
- **Optimism** - having a positive outlook, hoping for the best and preparing for success.

Social-awareness

- Empathy
- Service Orientation
- Organisational awareness

- **Empathy** - one of the pillars of the ability to form connections with others, understanding and acknowledging others' emotions;
- **Service Orientation** - being helpful, contributing to the group effort, and displaying good listening skills;
- **Organisational awareness** - the capability to explain yourself clearly and be conscious of how you are being understood, as well as recognising the level of comprehension of your audience.

Relationship management

- Role model
- Influence
- Conflict Management
- Recognising and supporting
- Assisting others
- Teamwork and effectively collaboration

- **Role model** – a good mentor and authority character.
- **Influence** - communicating points in persuasive, clear ways that efficiently motivate other people.
- **Conflict Management** - possessing the abilities to develop relationships, cooperate, and lead. The capacity to settle disputes, differences of opinion, and disagreements.
- **Recognising and supporting** - the necessity for change and making it happen.
- **Assisting others** - in developing their skills and knowledge.
- **Teamwork and effective collaboration** - working with others.

A leader tends to have a significant influence on the thoughts and motivation of people. He/she has the ability to stimulate optimism and confidence in the employees and lead them to constructive endeavours, also known for **resonance**. Conversely, they

can negatively affect employees to destruct, which is opposite to resonance, called **dissonance**.⁴

Leaders are directly observed regarding their body language and facial expressions (including other visual and auditive signs). **So, a leader needs to consider the non-verbal form of expressions, which may positively or negatively influence employees.** Therefore, if a leader talks about leading with staff conflict with a bemused look on his/her face, he/she will lead to incomprehension or even dissatisfaction from the staff. A leader must also act as a role model, supporting his/her statements, ideologies, and values with appropriate actions.⁴

As a leader, one also must be aware of one's abilities and limitations. It is challenging to accept support from a leader who is not self-aware. Leaders need to empathise with the employees' situations, emotions, aspirations, and motivations. The declining performance of a team member might be because of a few reasons. A disruptive employee might be facing motivation issues, and an employee who uses abusive language with others might lack confidence in his/her capabilities. A leader must discern facts and try to reach deeper levels and understand things beyond the evidence.^{1,4}

Emotional Intelligence is also important because the employees expect this competency from their leaders. An employee working closely with a leader would expect his/her understanding of the employee's situation and priorities. And not surprisingly, whether the leader does so or not affect the employees' level of commitment and performance at work. A leader ought to know and understand when he/she needs to be directive and when he/she needs to delegate. He/she must be aware of when the team members are working as one unit and when there are differences.

It is sometimes awkward to address the emotional aspects of transactions between people. Still, leaders need to understand the importance and relevance as it has a huge impact on performance results. While conducting evaluations and development dialogues, the feedback should be delivered acceptably. The leader requires to be

sensitive to the insecurities and apprehensions of the employees, which sometimes might be expressed and sometimes kept undisclosed. It is even more significant at the senior level as the senior executives find it hard to outline their anxieties and differences clearly, and the leader has to anticipate some of them.

So, to attract and retain talented employees and keep them motivated, a leader needs to brush up on his/her people abilities and emotional Intelligence, as all of them are not born with the charisma to hold people. Fortunately, emotional intelligence with practice and carefully directed efforts can be increased.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 4.2 - Communication

*“In addition to general language proficiency (adequate vocabulary and knowledge of syntax), **effective communication** involves the ability to listen and read with comprehension, to present one’s thoughts clearly both in speech and in writing, to accept that the perspectives of others may differ from one’s own, and to anticipate the effect of what one says or writes on listeners or readers.”¹*

Few skills are more vital to leadership than Communication. **Leaders must communicate** purpose, direction, and intent to all levels of the organisation while receiving the same from higher levels.²

Communication is a process with five descriptive steps:²

1. The process begins with someone who has an intended message for someone else;
2. The communicator sends the message verbally or in writing;
3. The object of Communication receives the message;
4. The recipient interprets the message, and the interpretation may or may not be the intended meaning of the sender;
5. The recipient gives the sender feedback needed to determine whether the message content and intent were interpreted correctly by responding to the message. If not, further Communication is required. Ensuring solid Communication and feedback can improve organisational effectiveness.

A communication, therefore, has three parts:²

- The sender
- The message
- The recipient

There might be more than one recipient, and the complexity of Communication means that each one may receive a slightly different message. **Two people may read very different things in selecting words and/or body language. It is also likely that neither of them will have a similar understanding as to the sender.**²

In **face-to-face interaction**, the sender and recipient roles are not different. The two roles will transmit back and forward information. Both parties communicate with each other, even in very subtle ways, such as through eye contact (or absence of) and overall body language. However, **in written Communication, the sender and recipient are more distinct.**²

Face-to-face interaction

In written Communication, the sender and recipient are more distinct

There is a wide range of ways we communicate, and more than one may occur at any given time.

The different categories of Communication include:²

- **Spoken or Verbal Communication** - includes face-to-face, telephone, radio or television and other media.
- **Non-Verbal Communication** includes gestures, body language, how we stand, how we dress or act, and our scent, among others. Several subtle ways exist that we communicate (possibly even accidentally) with other people. For example, the tone may give hints of the person's mood or emotional state, while gestures or hand signals can add to a spoken message.

- **Written Communication** - involves letters, e-mails, social media, books, magazines, the Internet and other media resource. Up until recently, a small number of writers and publishers were very powerful in conveying the written word. Currently, we can all write and publish our ideas online, which has led to an explosion of information and communication possibilities.
- **Visualisations** - graphs and charts, maps, logos, and other visualisations can all communicate messages.

The interpersonal communication process cannot be regarded as a phenomenon that merely “happens”. Instead, it should be noticed as a process that entails participants who negotiate their roles with each other, whether consciously or unconsciously.

The sender sends a message across a communication channel to one or more recipients. The **sender** should **encode** the message (the information transmitted) into a form appropriate to the communication channel. The **recipient decodes** the message to understand its meaning.²

Misunderstanding can take place at any step of the communication process. **Effective Communication includes reducing potential misunderstanding** and overcoming any barriers to Communication at each step in the communication process. An efficient

communicator understands their audience, chooses an appropriate communication channel, prepares their message for this specific channel, and encodes the message efficiently to reduce misinterpretation by the recipient(s). They will also look out for feedback from the recipient(s) to ensure that the message is understood and to correct any misunderstanding or confusion as soon as possible.²

Receivers can use Clarification and Reflection techniques as effective ways to ensure that the message sent has been understood correctly.

Figure 20. Effective Communication Process

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 4.3 - Goal Setting

The **goal-setting process** has rules to follow if the goals serve their purpose. Specific game rules need to be followed for personal or organisational goals to guide and motivate behaviour towards achievement and success. The main rule is that objectives must be **SMART**:^{1, 2, 3, 4}

Figure 21. SMART Objectives

Specific: This means that objectives should be specific. They should describe the desired result in a detailed, focused, and well-defined way. The following questions may help formulate **specific goals**:

- What results are we looking for?
- Is it obvious what the goal means?
- How will it be achieved, and what strategies will be observed?
- What are we going to do, for whom or with?
- Who will be responsible for what, and do we need anyone else to be involved?
- When do we want this to be finished?

When setting goals, especially for individuals, employ **action-orientated verbs** which describe what needs to be done to achieve the objectives. For example:

- Apply;
- Change;
- Determine;
- Identify;
- Instigate;
- Perform.

Measurable: Measurement is significant because it will let you know if a goal has been accomplished. To be measurable, a goal should explain an achievement or outcome which is or can be related to a percentage, number, frequency, or rate. Evidence will need to be obtained from a method, procedure, or system which has traced and recorded the results related to the goal. To help set measurable results, think about the desired result and which aspects can be measured. Consider if there is any scope for cross-comparison.

Consider the following:

- How will I realise that the change has happened?
- Can these measurements be obtained?

Achievable (agreed upon): An objective can be said to be achievable if the necessary resources are available or others have achieved similar results in related situations.

Questions to consider:

- Who will take the necessary actions?
- Do they have the required abilities to perform the task well?
- Are the resources (equipment, personnel, funding, time, etc.) available to accomplish this goal, or can they be obtained?
- Who will take responsibility for what?

“**Achievable**” suggests that those to whom it is assigned are willing and capable to achieve it. If goals are seen to be unachievable, the people responsible for them are expected to lose motivation and feel demoralised. People will be unwilling to invest energy and enthusiasm into something they do not believe possible. Understand that agreeing that a goal is achievable may include a commitment to offering a level of resources (for example, staff, time, money), without which the goal would not be achievable. This indicates that the goal would no longer be SMART for the individual, team, or organisation in changed situations. Also, setting goals too low can also cause demotivation and disillusionment. Stretching goals motivate to put effort and commitment into finding ways to reach the target. Most individuals will rise to a challenge if it is not excessive.

Relevant: The concepts of “realistic” and “achievable” are similar, and this may explain why some use the term “relevant” as an alternative. “**Realistic**” suggests a clear understanding of how the objective might be reached, that there are no circumstances or factors that would achieve the goal impossible or unlikely and that any potential obstacles and constraints have been considered. “**Relevant**” suggests that the goals set are appropriate to the individual or team and their job role and function or at the organisational level that align with the organisation's overall purpose and strategy.

Trackable (time-bound): It is necessary to set a date or time by which the objective should have been accomplished or completed, contributing to measurable objectives. For goals that may take weeks or even months to achieve fully, it is good practice to identify milestones or key steps and set deadlines to help keep progress towards the end objective on track. A deadline helps create the necessary urgency, prompts action, and focuses on those accountable for their commitments in agreeing to the goals. Not setting deadlines will decrease levels of urgency and motivation and may result in avoidable delays or failure to reach the objectives.

Providing direction and defining priorities: It is common sense that most people accomplish more when they know what is expected of them daily and over the long term. Think of your own experience and those times when you were most productive. Chances

are you had a clear idea of what was expected of you. With clear priorities, people can make effective decisions and take appropriate action to overcome challenges and accomplish tasks. It follows from this that an essential leadership task is to communicate goals and expectations to achieve organisational success. This Communication will differ if the person is a skilled member of the organisation or a new member.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 4.4 - Motivating People

What is Motivation?

Motivation implies people's needs, desires, wants, or drives. It is the process of motivating people to action to achieve the goals. In the work goal environment, the psychological aspects stimulating the people's behaviour can be the following:¹

The desire for money

Job-satisfaction

Success

Teamwork

Recognition

Others

One essential function of management is to create willingness amongst the employees to perform to the best of their skills. Consequently, the role of a leader is to arouse interest in the performance of employees in their work. The **process of motivation** involves three phases:^{1, 2}

1

A felt necessity or drive

2

A stimulus in which needs have to be aroused

3

When needs are fulfilled, the satisfaction or accomplishment of objectives.

Thus, we can say that motivation is a psychological phenomenon that means the needs and wants of the individuals should be grasped by framing an incentive plan.

Human behaviour is goal-directed. **Motivation affects goal-directed behaviour.** It is through motivation that requires can be managed and tackled intentionally. This can be assumed by understanding the hierarchy of needs of the leader. The needs of individuals serve as a driving force in human behaviour. Maslow has proposed “**The Needs Hierarchy Model**”^{1,2}

The needs have been categorised in the following order:^{1,2}

Figure 22. The Needs Hierarchy Model

1. **Physiological needs** - an individual's basic needs, including food, clothing, shelter, air, water, etc. These needs concern the survival and maintenance of human life.
2. **Safety needs** - these needs are also important for human beings. Everybody wants job security, protection against danger, the safety of property, etc.
3. **Social needs** - these needs emerge from society. Man is a social animal, so these needs are important: love, affection, belongingness, friendship, conversation, etc.
4. **Esteem needs** - these needs relate to the desire for self-respect, recognition, and respect from others.

5. Self-actualisation needs - are the needs of the highest order, found in those whose previous four needs are satisfied. This will include the need for social service, meditation, etc.

An incentive, or a stimulus, is an act or promise for greater action. **Incentives are provided in addition to wages.** It is extra remuneration or benefits to an employee in appreciation of achievement or work quality. Incentives may provide an employee's energy and interest to better work performance. It is expected that nobody acts without a purpose associated.^{1, 2}

Consequently, a hope for a reward is a powerful incentive to motivate employees. Besides monetary incentives, some other stimuli can drive a person to do better. This can involve job promotion, job satisfaction, job security, and pride for achievement. Hence, incentives can sometimes work to accomplish the goals of a concern.

The need for incentives can be various:

01

To increase productivity

02

To drive a work stimulus

03

To improve dedication in work performance

04

To psychologically fulfil a person, which leads to job satisfaction

05

To shape the behaviour or outlook of employees towards work

06

To induce enthusiasm and energy towards work

07

To obtain the maximum of their capacities, so they develop and use the maximum possible

Thus, **management** offers the two categories below of incentives to motivate employees:³

1. Monetary incentives - Type of incentives that satisfy the employees by providing them monetary rewards. Money has been recognised as a chief source of satisfying

the needs of people. Money is also helpful in satisfying social needs by possessing various material items. Therefore, money satisfies not only psychological needs but also security and social needs.

- 2. Non-monetary incentives** - Besides the monetary incentives, specific non-financial incentives can satisfy employees' ego and self-actualisation needs. The incentives that cannot be measured in terms of money are “non-monetary incentives”. Whenever a leader needs to satisfy the psychological needs of the employees, he/she uses non-financial incentives. Non-financial incentives can be of the following types (some examples):
 - a. Security of service** - Job security is an incentive that provides great motivation to employees. If his/her job is secured, he/she will put maximum effort into achieving the greatest. This also helps since the employee is very far off from mental tension, and he/she can give his/her best to the enterprise.
 - b. Praise or recognition** - Praise or recognition is another non-financial motivation that satisfies the ego necessities of the employees. Occasionally praise becomes more efficient than other incentives. The employees will react more to praise and try to concern with their best skills.
 - c. Promotion opportunities** - Promotion is an efficient tool to improve the spirit to work in concern. If the employees are given opportunities for progress and growth, they feel satisfied and more dedicated to the organisation.

A mixture of financial and non-financial incentives helps employees bring motivation and zeal to work in concern.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 4.5 - Building Teams

Teams have the potential to amass, organise, relocate, and disperse immediately. However, teams are an efficient tool for employee motivation. **Team development** generates a captivating environment by encouraging cooperation, interdependence, teamwork and building trust among team members. It is important to consider that teams improve and mature over a while.¹

The **four steps of team development** are the following:¹

- **Step 1: Forming.** During this step, group members may feel anxious and embrace a wait-and-see attitude. They will be formal towards each other, and there will be no clear idea of objectives or expectations. This is where the team must write its mission statement and clarify objectives. The most crucial aspect is that objectives should have a personal buy-in. Through this, the team will determine boundaries and what is required. Team members will start to know each other by doing non-conflict leading tasks. This creates a commitment towards one greater goal. Hence, during the forming step, the team members know each other and are at ease with them.
- **Step 2: Storming.** During this step, team members are keen to get going. Conflict can occur as people are likely to bring different ideas for achieving objectives. As such, they notice differences instead of similarities. This can lead to some members retrieving out mentally or physically. Also, Communication is important. Tensions may increase. As such, recognising accomplishments publicly seems crucial. It also becomes important to participate in meetings, and diversity needs to be respected. Hence, during this step, team members begin demonstrating their styles. They start getting impatient and probe into each other's space, leading to frustration and irritation. Control becomes the main concern.
- **Step 3: Norming.** In this stage, people begin to recognise how they are alike (and they realise they are in this together). Therefore, they tend to get more social and forget their focus on having a good time. This is the moment to help with training if pertinent. It becomes essential to encourage them to feel comfortable with each other. Also, the group needs to maintain focus on the objective. Thus, there is conflict

resolution and larger involvement of team members during the norming step. There is also a greater “we are” expression than an “I am” one.

- **Step 4: Performing.** This step is when team members are educated, skilled, and capable of doing their problem-solving. There is a need to look at them and challenge and develop them. The team is mature now. The members recognise their roles and responsibilities. They would need more feedback on processes. The members would be self-motivated and self-educated. Therefore, their efforts need to be acknowledged. Growth has to be promoted and encouraged. This is accomplished by providing new challenges to the team. Consequently, teams at the step of performing are self-controlling, loyal, practical and productive. Focus is there on both performances and production.

Forming an Effective Team:^{2,3}

This step is the typical attempt to make a successful work team. Success is usually hinged on taking all the steps discussed previously. We tend to surround ourselves with people who are just like us. If you choose a team, instead of organising a pre-formed team, you will look for a team of people with various strengths. Organising can be more subtle in the case of a team already in place. All the workgroups can be called together to discuss what objectives you want to achieve and how everybody can help. You will also find that imposing objectives on individuals does not work almost as well as having them tell you what objectives they will strive for. But setting goals is not easy work. Too often, end up being too unrealistic, too vague, impossible to measure, or just stretching into eternity without any deadline.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 4.6 - Conflict Management

Understanding Conflict - Meaning and Phases of Conflict

“Conflict arises whenever individuals have different values, opinions, needs, interests and are unable to find a middle way”.¹

Conflict is defined as a disagreement between individuals that could arise from a difference in understanding, thoughts, attitudes, requirements, interests, and even occasionally perceptions. A conflict may result in heated arguments, physical abuse and definitely loss of peace and harmony. A conflict can change relationships. Misunderstandings and ego disagreements may also cause conflicts. Every person has a different way of looking at things and reacting to various situations.²

When examining **workplace conflict**, one sees that there are **four basic types**. They are not different from those other conflicts you learned in freshman literature, except they all deal with conflict among people. They are:³

- Intrapersonal
- Interpersonal
- Intragroup
- Intergroup

Intrapersonal conflict is a conflict experienced by a single individual when his/her objectives, roles, and values diverge. A lawyer may feel a conflict of values when representing a defendant who knows to be guilty of the charges brought against himself/herself. An employee whose goal is to earn a promotion might feel an intrapersonal conflict when offered a position requiring him/her to be transferred to a different state. Or it could be a role conflict where an employee may have to choose between working one more shift or having dinner with family.³

As you might guess, **interpersonal conflict** is due to differences in objectives, values, and styles between two or more people who are necessary to interact and communicate. Since this type of conflict is between individuals, the conflicts can get very **personal**.³

For example, a board of directors may want to change the working schedules despite dissenting opinions among some board members.

Intragroup conflict could take place when they argue the pros and cons of taking such a risk. **Intergroup conflict** is when groups inside and outside an organisation disagree and argue on several issues. Conflict can also occur between two groups within the same organisation, which would also be considered an intergroup conflict. Within those kinds of conflict, one can experience **horizontal conflict** (a conflict with others at the same peer level as the individual) or **vertical conflict** (a conflict with a leader or an employee).³

Phases of Conflict

A conflict has five phases, namely:

1. **Prelude to conflict** - It entails all the aspects which possibly occur in a conflict among people. Lack of coordination, dissimilarity in cultures and religions, differences in interests, and educational background are instrumental factors that can lead to conflict.
2. **Triggering Event** - No conflict occurs on its own. There has to be an event that triggers the conflict (personal, organisational, cultural).
3. **Initiation Phase** - The initiation phase is when the conflict has begun already. For example, heated arguments, verbal disagreements, and abuses are warning signs that suggest a starting conflict.
4. **Differentiation Phase** - When people voice out their disagreements against each other. The reasons for the conflict are raised.
5. **Resolution Phase** - A conflict leads to nowhere. People must attempt to compromise to some degree and solve the conflict quickly. This phase explores the many alternatives to resolve the conflict.

Conflicts can occur in various types, such as verbal conflict, emotional conflict, religious conflict, social conflict, organisational conflict, personal conflict, community conflict, etc.

- **Conflict Management Skills:**²

Conflict management plays a significant part in preventing conflicts between people. How does a conflict arise? **When people strongly disagree with each other's opinions and ideas, the probability of a conflict occurring is high.** A conflict begins when people think on different lines and find it very difficult to accept each other's ideas. Conflict must be avoided as it destroys peace, lowers productivity as well as demotivates people. All aspects of a fight must be explored, and attempts must be made to prevent a conflict. **A conflict is not simple to control; an individual needs specific skills to do that.**

Let us study the skills in detail.²

- **Effective Communication Skills:**

Effective communication competencies are of the greatest importance in preventing conflicts. While interacting with others, you need to take special care of your speech and how you speak. **Never shout at anyone, even if you disagree with them.** Always communicate in a polite but convincing way. Greet others with a warm smile. It works. Be very specific in your speech. Do not use complicated words and confuse others. Keep control of your tongue, and do not use words that might hurt the sentiments of others. Avoid using abusive languages.

- **Listening Skills:**

Always be a **good listener**. Do not rush to conclusions and suppose things on your own. Always listen to the other version of the story. An individual must not give his/her expert remarks unless and until it is very clear about what the other person wants.

- **Discussion:**

Do not just follow the rumours - discuss them with others. Differences can occur anytime, but fighting would not provide any solution. **It is always better to discuss**

the conflict with an open attitude. All the involved people must contribute, and efforts must be made to find an alternative. Invite those involved in the conflict and never ignore anyone as it would never solve the problem. Each person has the right to communicate his/her views, and a central way needs to be found.

- **Patience:**

Patience is a virtue, and you should be patient if the objective is to avoid conflicts. There would be people at work and at home who would try to provoke you to fight. Never get affected and influenced. Always follow your instincts and encourage what is right. Learn to control and manage your emotions. Do not lose your temper, as it would only worsen the situation.

- **Impartiality:**

An individual needs to be unbiased to avoid conflicts. Stick to what is correct and never support what is wrong. For example, do not support your friend if he/she is not right - any individual must be corrected if you feel he/she is wrong. Listen to all the people involved and do not ignore anyone just because you do not know them.

- **Never Criticise:**

Make the other person understand if he/she is wrong. Do not criticise as it would hurt their feelings. Other people might not be as intelligent as you are, but you have no right to make fun of them. People will look up to you if you guide them properly and make them realise their mistakes.

- **Positive Attitude:**

A positive attitude is essential to avoid fights and conflicts. Never take part in the blame game. People are bound to make mistakes but never try to blame anyone else's shoulders. If you do not agree with anyone's views, discuss with her/him face-

to-face, and the person will like it. Do not always find faults in others and be a little more adjusting as life is all about adjustments.

- **Ignore Others:**

People must try to embrace the middle path attitude, which considers the interests of one and all. Do not unnecessarily waste your energy on a too adamant person unwilling to cooperate. Ignore the overly demanding individual as it would resolve half of your problems.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 4.7 - Coaching

Generally speaking, **coaching** is a process that permits a person or group of people to contemplate and achieve awareness of who they are, their strengths and limitations, what is important to them, the choices open to them and what path to take to make the changes they want in their work/life.¹

Dissimilar to training, where the emphasis is on the trainer communicating their knowledge to you, **coaching concentrates on helping the coachee to take accountability for recognising their objectives, evaluating their strengths and areas for growth, and identifying their solutions for moving forwards.** This is accomplished by the coach offering a safe and non-judgmental environment, asking thought-provoking issues and listening to support the coachee to reflect, explore and make decisions.¹

People participate in coaching for several reasons. It can help them make modifications in their life, business or career, improve their performance, and relationships with others or develop specific competencies.

To further clarify what **coaching** is, here are a couple of definitions:

- *“Coaching is unlocking a person’s potential to maximise their own performance. It is helping them learn rather than teaching them”.*²

- *“Coaching is ‘a process that enables learning and development to occur and thus performance to improve’. To be successful, a coach requires a knowledge and understanding of the process as well as the variety of styles, skills, and techniques that are appropriate to the context in which coaching takes place”.*

- **Directive Versus Non-Directive Coaching:**²

There are also distinct methods to perform coaching, and this is where the definitions of coaching become hazy.

Non-directive coaching is when the coach asks questions to allow the person to find his/her solutions. A non-directive coach will definitely not offer advice and hardly even give suggestions. However, skilful questioning will help see the situation from a different perspective, gain clarity, uncover options, challenge inconsistencies, and hold accountable for the actions.

The benefit of non-directive coaching is that people take full responsibility for their solutions rather than “doing what you have been told to do.” With this approach, people feel empowered to make changes in their lives, reflecting in their confidence bolstered. On the other hand, **directive coaching is when the coach proposes solutions, options, tools, and methods.** People may enjoy being offered solutions; however, the problem is that although that solution may have worked for the other person, it may not be adequate for another. Consequently, people may not feel entirely committed to the solution provided.

- **Coaching Versus Mentoring:**³

The concepts of **mentoring** and **coaching** are frequently applied interchangeably and sometimes get confused. A **mentor** is usually more experienced than the person they are helping (mentee), who can draw upon their experience to help the mentee progress. They can, thus, present them with the ropes, help them if things get tough and answer questions. But a mentor may also rely on broad styles within a mentoring relationship. For example, a person with a new role at work might have a mentor who has performed

before or been in the organisation for a more prolonged period. Also, at times offering advice and guidance, they may engage in a coaching style later in the relationship, making open-ended questions to support their mentee to reflect on things for themselves, improving their confidence and making decisions.

Coaching is, therefore, about allowing reflection, deepening awareness and bringing meaningful actions.

COACHING

MENTORING

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

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What did I learn?

- ◇ Definition and characteristics of Emotional Intelligence
- ◇ The four important aspects of Emotional Intelligence
- ◇ Definition and characteristics of Communication
- ◇ Different categories of Communication
- ◇ Definition and characteristics of Goal Setting
- ◇ SMART objectives
- ◇ Definition and characteristics of Motivation
- ◇ The needs in the Need Hierarchy Model
- ◇ The four steps of Team development
- ◇ Definition and characteristics of Conflict
- ◇ The four basic types of Conflict
- ◇ Characteristics of Conflict management
- ◇ Definition and characteristics of Coaching
- ◇ Types of Coaching

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